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CHESS
SET UP

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1. Introduction: Published Articles' Dissemination Strategy

The publication of articles (including **divulgarion articles, press releases and scientific papers**) have been treated as an effective tool helping with the Communication and Dissemination Plan of CHESSE SETUP project, exposed in **Deliverable 7.1**. The communication and dissemination articles about CHESSE SETUP project and/or system have helped to disseminate the project's objectives, development, achievements, and results all along the duration of the project.

*Figure 1. Strategic objectives of communication and dissemination.
(Source: D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan, CHESSE SETUP Project)*

At the beginning of the project, the Consortium decided to broaden the width of potential stakeholders and target audience, ranging from the building sector (identified since the beginning), to the civil society, a conceptual entity including non-technical recipients such as the media and end users. In **Deliverable 7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan** more information about the engagement's reasons and analysis can be consulted.

Figure 2. Stakeholders and target groups for communication and dissemination. (Source: D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan, CHESSETUP Project)

As it appears on the stakeholder's range, the diversity of the audience induces a differential treatment. In order to reach every stakeholder's category, we have adapted the content of the messages spread, as well as the media carrying it.

The communication channels have been the website, social media, newsletters, clustering activities, one-to-one communication, conferences, workshops, events and the Press or media.

Along the implementation of CHESSETUP project:

- **3 DIVULGATION ARTICLES about CHESSETUP Project in particular** have been written for publication in specialized journals/magazines/portals and listed on CHESSETUP project website. Those articles have been written in English and translated to Spanish and/or French. The frequency has been **one per year**, except for the period between 2017-2018 due to the pilots' construction delays and lack of results.
 - **1st Divuligation article:** finished on July 2016 and finally published in August 2016 in **"BUILD UP: The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings"**.
 - **2nd Divuligation article:** April 2019, published in the magazine **"Energías Renovables"** (Renewable Energies) in Spanish.
 - **3rd Divuligation Article:** October 2020, published in the 7th Volume of the Project Repository Journal (PRj) of EDMA - European Dissemination Media Agency.

- **6 extra DIVULGATION ARTICLES about the CHESSE SETUP Pilots and System** have been written by the partners responsible of every Pilot case. The articles have been published in specialized journals and/or magazines and listed in the project website. These articles were published when the opportunity arose and specifically at the last phase of the project, when the construction works and benefits of the pilot cases could be exposed:
 - **Article “CHESSE SETUP afavoreix l’autosuficiència a nivell energètic” (CHESSE SETUP promotes energy self-sufficiency)** published online in **Anthesis Lavola News Site** in January 2019 – LaVola Pilot.
 - **Article “Etopia Corby starts to show”** published online in **The Construction Index** in August 2019 – Corby Pilot.
 - **Article “Etopia unveils first completed modular eco home at its London commuter village”** published online in **Building Products magazine** in August 2019 – Corby Pilot.
 - **Article “Etopia completes modular eco home”** published online in **PBC Today (UK)** in August 2019 – Corby Pilot.
 - **Article/Case Study of Corby Pilot (Etopia)** published within **TCPA New Communities Guide for Local Authorities on Modern Methods of Construction (UK)** in April 2020 – Corby Pilot.
 - **Article/Case Study of Sant Cugat Pilot** published in the **International Energy Agency – Solar Heating & Cooling Programme report “Existing PVT systems and solutions”** in May 2020 – Sant Cugat Pilot.

- **4 PRESS RELEASES about CHESSE SETUP Project in particular** have been developed directly by the Consortium within the Grant Agreement framework. This press releases were sent to media agencies or EU portals and also published on the website. The aim was to provide a clear message to all kind of media, in order to raise awareness concerning the project’s objectives and achievements. The Press Releases were sent to “BUILD UP: The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings” and published here and in CHESSE SETUP website. The frequency has been **one per year**, also except for the period between 2017-2018 due to the pilots’ construction delays and lack of results.
 - **1st Press Release:** wrote on July 2016 and released on August 2016.
 - **2nd Press Release:** wrote on April 2018 and released on June 2018.
 - **3rd Press Release:** September 2019 (launched with the Email Marketing Tool, sent to all the subscribers in our website).
 - **4th Press Release:** September 2020.

- **6 Extra PRESS RELEASES about CHESS SETUP Project and the Pilots in particular, externally edited** but with validation by the coordinators of CHESS SETUP pilots and Lead partner. These press releases can be found online in various sites and online/written press such as local newspapers or public and private organizations platforms interested in sustainability and the built environment. Here you can find **a selected set with 8 relevant examples**, although it is possible to find online more representation and citations about the project:
 - **Press Release “The ZEM on the Rambla del Celler in Sant Cugat del Vallès, a reference model for the International Energy Agency”**: May 2020, published in Barcelona Provincial Council (Diputació de Barcelona) Sustainable Magazine.
 - **Press Release “The International Energy Agency puts Sant Cugat as a reference model”**: May 2020, published in Nació Sant Cugat Newspaper.
 - **Press Release in form of interview “Lavola cosustainability”**: published in EsAgua platform.
 - **Press Release “Project Etopia unveils finished Corby modular house”**: August 2019, published in Housing Today media brand news.

- **4 SCIENTIFIC PAPERS** have been published related to **heat pumps** and considering CHESS SETUP system case studies and implementation as a source. They have been published thanks to the research carried out by our partner Ulster University, Centre for Sustainable Technologies, represented by professor Neil J. Hewitt. In the website of the project you can find the links to the official publication in the specialized magazine or research portal where they have been accepted and published, under a Creative Common license and Open Access. The papers have been published at the **last phase** of the project due to the needed research time to be able to write and present quality conclusions worthy of presentation, review and publication to scientific journals.
 - **1st Scientific paper**: “High temperature air source heat pump coupled with thermal energy storage: comparative performances and retrofit analysis”, February 2019.
 - **2nd Scientific paper**: “Techno-economic assessment of cascade air-to-water heat pump retrofitted into residential buildings using experimentally validated simulations”, September 2019.
 - **3rd Scientific paper**: “Domestic demand-side response: the challenge for heat pumps in a future UK - decarbonized heating market”, August 2019.
 - **4th Scientific paper**: “Tariff-based load shifting for domestic cascade heat pump with enhanced system energy efficiency and reduced wind power curtailment”, January 2020.

More detailed information about all these publications can be consulted in next sections (2. Divulcation Articles, 3. Press Releases, 4. Scientific Papers), where the link to the publications is provided.

Additionally, all publications (i.e. divulgation articles, scientific papers, public deliverables, newsletters, conference papers, etc.) have been published in an **Open Access platform** named **zenodo** indexed in OpenAire. Link [here](#).

Finally, in Figure 3, a synthetized **calendar of publications** regarding the **divulgation articles, press releases and scientific papers** is shown:

Figure 3. Calendar of CHESSE SETUP divulgation articles, press releases and scientific papers' publication

2. CHESS SETUP Divulcation Articles

CHESS SETUP Project Divulcation Articles

The 3 Divulcation Articles published by CHESS SETUP EU funded project are summarized as follows and were also promoted via our **social media channels** (Twitter and LinkedIn):

- **1st Divulcation Article: edited on July 2017 and published on September 2017 in "BUILD UP: The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings".**

The 1st divulcation article presented the CHESS SETUP Project for the first time in the press, exposing the challenge, main goals, the system, the monitoring strategy, and main benefits. It was co-written by the consortium and edited by Edenway, the partner leading WP7-Communication and capitalization activities. It was sent and published in "BUILD UP: The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings". This press channel was selected because BUILD UP web portal is intended to reap the benefits of Europe's collective intelligence on energy reduction in buildings for all relevant audiences, motivating them to exchange best working practices and knowledge and to transfer tools and resources (BUILD UP, About the portal).

1st Divulcation article
CHESS SETUP: the project working to reduce buildings' energy consumption

CHESS SETUP is a project designing a solution to provide energy from renewable sources to buildings. The building sector is one of the most resource consuming sectors as it accounts for 40% of energy consumption and 36% of CO2 emissions in the EU. The European Union has set ambitious targets in order to reduce the GHG emissions and the building sector has to do its part, with new buildings required to be "nearly zero-energy buildings" (NZEB) by 2020. By using energy more efficiently, a reduction on energy bills and reliance on external energy suppliers can be achieved while helping protect the environment.

To address this challenge, CHESS SETUP, a ten-member consortium, designed a solution relying on:

- **Hybrid solar panels** generating heat to be stored and used for domestic hot water and/or heating in addition to electricity that can be used by the building's systems and appliances.
- **A hot water tank** to store the thermal energy produced by the hybrid solar panels, especially in summer.
- **A heat pump** to provide domestic hot water and/or heating from the hot water tank to the building at high efficiencies.

The system will therefore work on a **seasonal mode**: the heat produced by the solar hybrid panels mostly in the summer will be stored to heat the building needs when required.

The team is working to install the system in **three different sites** in the United Kingdom and in Spain, **sizing** the elements according to the buildings' characteristics such as the solar irradiation, energy demands, and available surface for the installation of solar panels installation and the thermal storage tank.

The installation will be **monitored and controlled** to manage the system efficiently based on key data such as available heat energy, weather forecast and electricity prices to **optimize** the energy flows within the system.

CHESS SETUP can allow significant energy savings for the buildings: the energy produced on-site will be consumed on-site or reverted to the power grid if necessary. CHESS SETUP could bring key solutions for our future: a **self-consumption system** that could drive us towards NZEB, energy independence, a higher productivity of the grids and a low-carbon society.

Link to the Divulcation article published in BUILD UP [here](#).

Link to the Divulcation article uploaded in CHESS SETUP website [here](#). It is also downloadable in **French and in Spanish** languages.

On February 2020, this first CHESS SETUP divulcation article has been updated and re-published/re-launched again in the Explore Section of BUILD UP Portal.

Link to the re-launched Divulcation article publication [here](#).

- 2nd Divulcation Article: April 2019, published in “Revista Energías Renovables” (Renewable Energy Magazine).

The 2st divulgation article was called “Cómo conseguir un sistema eficiente y sostenible de producción de calor” (How to get an efficient and sustainable system of heat production), exposing CHESSE SETUP project and system in a detailed way, presenting the origin, the goals, benefits, the system, and the 3 pilot cases. It was written by the Lead Partner, Barcelona Ecologia (Moisés Morató and Sergio Sánchez). The Spanish version was sent and published in the magazine [Energías Renovables](#). The magazine reaches the professionals in the sector of renewable energies - promoters, manufacturers and distributors, technicians, installers and maintenance and service companies - responsible for the energy and environment departments of the administrations, research centers, professors and students of universities and institutes, NGOs, journalists and individuals with a particular interest in the development of renewable energies (About us, Energías Renovables).

Link to the Divulcation article published in the magazine [here](#).

Link to the Divulcation article uploaded in CHESSE SETUP website [here](#).

- 3rd Divulcation Article:

The 3rd divulgation article will be published in the 7th Volume of the Project Repository Journal (PRJ) of EDMA – European Dissemination Media Agency (October 2020). This article written by the lead partner, Barcelona Ecologia, will present the project path, its key exploitation results, conclusions and lessons learned.

The Project Repository Journal (PRJ) is the EDMA’s flagship open access publication dedicated to showcasing funded science and research throughout Europe. It is distributed free of charge, digitally, every 3 months to circa 150,000 people across Europe (plus a second distribution of circa 70,000 covering North America, China and Japan). Therefore, the article will reach a large number of audiences, specially coming

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TERMINA

Cómo conseguir un sistema eficiente y sostenible de producción de calor

El proyecto europeo Chess Setup, en el marco del programa Horizonte 2020, busca implementar y promover un sistema eficiente y rentable compuesto por captación de energía solar mediante paneles híbridos y fotovoltaicos, almacenamiento de energía y utilización de bomba de calor capaz de satisfacer las demandas de climatización y agua caliente sanitaria (ACS) de las edificaciones.

Un sistema propuesto por el consorcio Chess Setup se va a implementar en tres edificios en los edificios con diferentes climatizaciones: San Cugat del Valles (Barcelona), Maslles (Barcelona) y Carby (Baixa Urbana). Además, está operando para una plantación de monitorización y control que utiliza un algoritmo para optimizar y mejorar su operación en función a las previsiones de la energía, la producción climatización y requerimientos de los usuarios.

La utilización de bombas de calor emplea un sistema de almacenamiento de energía solar mediante paneles híbridos y fotovoltaicos, almacenamiento de energía y utilización de bomba de calor.

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De 2019. Para cada vivienda se ha instalado un consumo energético medio de 2.000 kWh anuales. En el año 2019, se instalaron en cada vivienda un sistema de captación de energía solar mediante paneles híbridos y fotovoltaicos, almacenamiento de energía y utilización de bomba de calor. El sistema cuenta con una capacidad de 15.4 MW. El sistema cuenta con un CSP (colector solar) de 100 metros cuadrados. No se espera que el sistema cubra el 90% de la demanda total de agua caliente de los edificios, lo que representa un ahorro energético de hasta el 40% de la demanda total de energía del edificio, con un ahorro en emisiones de CO₂ de hasta el 30%.

Edificio de oficinas en Maslles (España)
El tercer pilar es el Edificio de la empresa multinacional Lerma Maslles, Barcelona.

from the European ecosystem, from policy makers and public sector to funding agencies and research councils (European Commission, Government agencies and departments throughout Europe, America and Asia, Municipalities, local and central government departments including some Ministries responsible for science, education, research, transport, health, energy, environment, defence, etc., European funding agencies and Research Councils, Universities, research centres, Institutes, labs, Associations, Academia, Global NCP's, NGO's, project co-ordinators).

CHESSETUP Pilot and System Extra Divuligation Articles

The 6 extra Divuligation Articles about the CHESSETUP pilots and system are summarized as follows and were also listed in the project website and promoted via our **social media channels** (Twitter and LinkedIn):

- **Article "CHESSETUP afavoreix l'autosuficiència a nivell energètic" (CHESSETUP promotes energy self-sufficiency): January 2019, published in Anthesis Lavola News Site – LaVola Pilot.**

Article presenting CHESSETUP project as a system promoting energy self-sufficiency in buildings and exposing LaVola pilot experience in a tertiary/office building (Manlleu, Spain), in particular.

Link to the article [here](#).

- **Article "Etopia Corby starts to show": August 2019, published in The Construction Index – Corby Pilot.**

Article in the Construction Index - Construction News about Project Etiopia: The homes at Etopia Corby in Priors Hall Park uses a combined heat supply system using solar energy and heat pumps (CHESSETUP).

Link to the article [here](#).

- Article “Etopia unveils first completed modular eco home at its London commuter village”: August 2019, published online in Building Products magazine – Corby Pilot.

The article exposes Etopia Project Corby as a scheme embracing the CHESSE SETUP (Combined Heat Supply System by using Solar Energy and Heat Pumps), Horizon 2020 programme which aims to implement a reliable and efficient heating system that can supply buildings via renewable energy sources.

Link to the article [here](#).

- Article “Etopia completes modular eco”: August 2019, published online in PBC Today – Corby Pilot.

The article exposes Etopia Project Corby and CHESSE SETUP in the same way as the previous article.

Link to the article [here](#).

- Article/Case Study of Corby Pilot (Etopia): April 2020, published within TCPA New Communities Guide for Local Authorities on Modern Methods of Construction (UK) – Corby Pilot.

The article/case study is presented in this Practical Guide that introduces emerging opportunities and challenges around using Modern Methods of Construction (MMC) to deliver world-class new communities for everyone. MMC is considered essential to meet the UK’s ambitious target of enabling the delivery of 300,000 homes per year by the mid-2020s and net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050. The government is investing in research on and delivery of non-traditional construction techniques and CHESSE SETUP and Earth Bank systems used in Corby Pilot (Etopia Project) is stated as a best practice in the Guide, with a special place being its cover image.

Link to the article/case study [here](#).

- **Article/Case Study of Sant Cugat Pilot: May 2020, published in the International Energy Agency – Solar Heating & Cooling Programme report “Existing PVT systems and solutions”– Sant Cugat Pilot.**

The International Energy Agency exposes in its report Sant Cugat Sport Center pilot of CHESSE SETUP as a global reference among the 30 reference projects in operation of hybrid solar panels (PV-T). In this case, with an optimal combination of seasonal thermal storage, heat pump and PVT.

Link to the article/study case [here](#).

3. CHESSE SETUP Press Releases

CHESSE SETUP Project Press Releases

The 4 Press Releases by CHESSE SETUP EU funded project were released in “**BUILD UP: The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings**” and in CHESSE SETUP website. All press releases were also promoted via our **social media channels** (Twitter and LinkedIn):

- **1st Press Release. Birth of CHESSE SETUP:** wrote on July 2016 and released on August 2016 in BUILD UP.

The 1st press release presented the kick-off of CHESSE SETUP project meeting in Barcelona as well as the consortium, idea, goals, the pilot’s cases and the budget (90% funded by the EU).

 Funded by the European Union

 Funded by the European Union

PRESS RELEASE
CHESSE SETUP, a European project seeking buildings' energy self-sufficiency

Low temperature thermal demand (Domestic Hot Water and heating) is worth 50% of the apartment buildings' needs. A new European project looks for the most efficient solution to cover up this demand with solar energy, even during the months with the lowest level of solar radiation.

Barcelona, 6th of July 2016 – Today starts the European Project CHESSE SETUP with its kick-off meeting in Barcelona. The project is part of the Horizon 2020 Program, 2014-2020 Work Programme "Secure, Clean and Efficient Energy".

CHESSE SETUP stands for "Combined Heat Supply System by using Solar Energy and heat pumps". It is an evolution of a former project implemented by the Urban Ecology Agency of Barcelona: SCACS (Storage and domestic hot water System by means of Seasonal Thermal Storage).

 SCACS model outline, envisaged by the project
 Picture of the partners involved in the project, during the kick-off Meeting in Barcelona

Link to the press release in BUILD UP [here](#).

Link to the press release uploaded in CHESSE SETUP website [here](#).

- **2nd Press Release. CHESSE SETUP in practice:** wrote on April 2018 and released on June 2018 in BUILD UP in a summarised form, and in CHESSE SETUP website in an extended form.

The 2nd press release presented a synthesis of the partners' contribution at this stage, the pilots' state and two achievements which were the report on regulatory framework, and the control and communication system designed by the partner Wattia.

Press release

CHESSE SETUP is bringing a smart renewable-generation heating system for different facilities of 3 European cities in Spain and the UK.

The project has evaluated a crucial aspect of the ecosystem in which it is being developed: the regulatory framework of thermal storage in both countries. Another key result is the completion of the energy monitoring system to be implemented in each project's use case.

Barcelona, April 23 2018 - Currently already in the second half of the project's three years duration, all three pilots are being built under the requirements of CHESSE SETUP's partners from Corby (UK), to Sant Cugat del Valles and Madrid (Spain).

Picture of the partners involved in the project, during the Warsaw Meeting at the European Commission in Brussels

On the other hand, CHESSE SETUP's Control and Monitoring System (CMS) has already been designed by Wattia-Innova. The aim of the CMS is to efficiently control the energy flows within the system (production, storage, conditioning, and final customer). In addition, the monitoring system will take into account auxiliary measurements and management signals needed for controlling the individual devices of the system as well as for the alarm generation.

Subsystem to be monitored in the CHESSE SETUP project

Currently, the pilot cases are still being constructed, which means that the final controls and monitoring may therefore vary from the generic CHESSE SETUP case and will be adapted to each scenario accordingly. Moreover, note that there are variations among the pilots, for example in the form of the storage being geothermal in Corby, and a large-scale use case in Sant Cugat. At this moment in time and considering the limitations of the pilots, the possibilities of optimizing the CHESSE SETUP system for each scenario are being considered and analyzed in more detail.

This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 680556

Link to the extended press release uploaded in CHESSE SETUP website [here](#).

Link to the summarised press release in BUILD UP [here](#).

- **3rd Press Release. CHESSE SETUP is advancing:** released in September 2019 through the Email Marketing tool of CHESSE SETUP website to all our subscribers, in order to analyse, in this occasion, the impact it would have with the analytics the tool provided.

The 3rd press release presented mainly the advancements in the pilot cases and presented the first positive results being achieved by CHESSE SETUP system. It also announced the decision of the DG for Research and Innovation of the European Commission that selected CHESSE-SETUP's H2020 project as an ideal beneficiary from SSERR (Support Service for Exploitation of Research Results).

The Email Marketing tool analytics provided us with the following data: 90% of delivery rate and 25% of opening rate.

Link to the press release via CHESSE SETUP website marketing tool [here](#).

- **4th Press Release. CHESSE SETUP Outcomes:** wrote and released in September 2020 in BUILD UP, Barcelona Ecologia News Site and the project website.

The 4th press release was the last press release during the EU funding phase of the project. It presented the project path and its main outcomes. Finally, it also announced the Online Final Conference, inviting the readers to join, and the publication of the Final Brochure of CHESSE SETUP, summarizing the project, the system and its results.

Link to the press release in BUILD UP [here](#).

Link to the press release uploaded in CHESSE SETUP website [here](#).

Extra CHESSE SETUP Project and Pilot Press Releases

Various **externally edited** press releases but with validation by the coordinators of CHESSE SETUP pilots and Lead partner have been published throughout the project. Here you can find a **list and link to a selected set of 8 relevant examples**, published in **local newspapers or public and private organizations platforms** interested in sustainability and the built environment:

- **Press Release “CHESSE SETUP, un projecte europeu a la recerca de l'autosuficiència tèrmica dels edificis” (CHESSE SETUP, an European project to research thermal self-sufficiency in buildings):** July 2016, published in Barcelona Ecologia Press Release website section. Link [here](#).

CHESSE SETUP Project launching and kick-off meeting were the main topic of this press release by Barcelona Ecologia, lead partner of the project. It announced the context, goals, the consortium, the pilots, among others.

- **Press Release “The ZEM on the Rambla del Cellar in Sant Cugat del Vallès, a reference model for the International Energy Agency”:** May 2020, published in Barcelona Provincial Council (Diputació de Barcelona) Sustainable Magazine. Link [here](#).
- **Press Release “The International Energy Agency puts Sant Cugat as a reference model”:** May 2020, published in Nació Sant Cugat Newspaper. Link [here](#).

Sant Cugat pilot and the CHESSE SETUP project is the interest of these two last press releases, interested in achieving sustainability. They announced the positive effects of

PRESS RELEASE 4: CHESSE SETUP OUTCOMES

After many months of hard work between all the 20 partners, CHESSE SETUP H2020 funded project is coming to an end with an overall success.

CHESSE SETUP was born with the idea to respond to the increasing heating and domestic hot water demand in the building sector considering that, in Europe, most of the thermal energy is produced from fossil fuels (86%) and only 13% comes from renewable energy (European Commission, Heating and Cooling Facts and Figure, 2018).

The project has designed a solution relying on an innovative and optimal combination of:

- **Hybrid solar panels** generating heat to be stored and used for domestic hot water and/or heating in addition to electricity that can be used by the building's systems and appliances.
- **A seasonal thermal energy storage** to store the thermal energy produced by the hybrid solar panels, especially in summer.
- **A heat pump**, to provide domestic hot water and/or heating from the hot water tank to the building at high efficiencies.

The 3 project pilots (sports centre in Spain, office building in Spain and dwellings in United Kingdom) have proved the positive effects and the economical feasibility of CHESSE SETUP-system.

CHESSE SETUP key exploitation results represent an important achievement into the European energetic transition and a commitment towards a sustainable development.

CHESS SETUP system in Sant Cugat pilot and mention its presence in the report "Existing PVT systems and solutions" by International Energy Agency – Solar Heating & Cooling Programme.

- **Press Release in form of interview "Lavola cosustainability"**: published in EsAgua platform.

The interview released to this platform press section was made to the Director of LaVola. The release mentioned that the CHESS SETUP partner is working to ensure that the consumption of their headquarters is 100% renewable. Highlighting for this their participation in the European project CHESS-SETUP of the Horizon 2020 program that would allow the company to innovate in issues of energy accumulation. Link [here](#).

- **Press Release "Project Etopia unveils finished Corby modular house"**: August 2019, published in Housing Today media brand news.

It announces that Project Etopia development (Corby pilot), once finished, each onsite home will be hooked up to an energy heating supply and storage system, CHESS SETUP, which is part of the renewable and sustainable energy programme of Horizon 2020, the EU's €80bn innovation and research programme. Link [here](#).

4. CHESSE SETUP Scientific Papers

4 Scientific Papers related to heat pumps research, and with CHESSE SETUP project as a source of reference and financial support, have been finally published during the project period, under a Creative Common license and Open Access. The papers have been created and co-written thanks to the research carried out by our partner Ulster University, Centre for Sustainable Technologies (represented by Professor Neil J. Hewitt).

In the acknowledgment section of the papers, the authors give thanks for the **financial contribution from the European Commission via H2020, CHESSE-SETUP project [Grant No.: 680556]**.

The **impact factor and citation score** (or number of downloads as an alternative, if it is not possible to retrieve the first, due to the different characteristics of the platform for academic studies) can be consulted in section 5.

- **Scientific paper 1:**

“High temperature air source heat pump coupled with thermal energy storage: comparative performances and retrofit analysis”

Energy Procedia

Volume 158, February 2019, Pages 3878-3885

Published in: Energy Procedia, Volume 158, February 2019, Pages 3878-3885.

Author/s: Khoa Xuan Le, Ming Jun Huang, Nikhilkumar Shah, Christopher Wilson, Neil J. Hewitt.

Abstract: This paper presents the performance analysis and retrofit assessment of a domestic high temperature air source heat pump coupled with thermal energy storage in terms of different system configurations. TRNSYS simulations were used to model the dynamic system, which has been validated against field trial results. The validated models were then simulated with different system configurations under the same boundary conditions to assess its performances. Simulated results showed that continuous coupling between the heat pump and storage to heat the house had the worst performance, while the operation of only the heat pump heating the house obtained the highest efficiency. Although the heat pump cannot compete with the gas boilers in terms of running costs, between 6.6% and 33% of carbon cut can be achieved if the heat pump was retrofitted.

Link to the scientific paper [here](#).

Link to the scientific paper through CHESSE SETUP website section [here](#).

- Scientific paper 2:

“Techno-economic assessment of cascade air-to-water heat pump retrofitted into residential buildings using experimentally validated simulations”

Applied Energy
Volume 250, 15 September 2019, Pages 633-652

Published in: ELSEVIER - Applied Energy, Volume 2500, May 2019, Pages 633-652

Author/s: Khoa Xuan Le, Ming Jun Huang, Nikhilkumar N. Shah, Christopher Wilson, Paul Mac Artain, Raymond Byrne, Neil J. Hewitt.

Abstract: Cascade air-to-water heat pumps have better overall efficiency than single-stage air-to-water heat pumps when operating at low ambient temperatures for high temperature water supply. While many studies in the literature investigated the specific features of equipment performance of cascade heat pumps, there is little information about retrofit applications of these heat pumps in residential buildings using experimentally validated dynamic building simulations. In this study, the techno-economic assessment of a variable capacity cascade air-to-water heat pump retrofitted into residential buildings is conducted by means of experimentally validated TRNSYS simulations. The cascade heat pump coupled with thermal energy storage operating in different scenarios is further studied. Laboratory and field trial results were obtained to develop and validate a cascade heat pump model integrated with a dynamic building simulation model. Regarding the heat pump system without storage, the predicted annual COPs were almost below 2.5 at ambient temperatures of from $-11.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $29.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, even the heat pump adopted weather compensation control. Simulation results also indicated that the cascade heat pump could not defeat gas boilers and high-efficiency oil boilers (90%) in terms of operating costs, but there were reductions (from 14% to 57%). As for the heat pump coupled with storage, simulation results showed that at ambient temperatures of between $-5.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $23.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the continuous coupling between the heat pump and the storage revealed the lowest annual performance (actual COP of 1.41), while the direct heating obtained the highest efficiency (actual COP of 2.12) followed by the load-shifting (actual COP of 1.88).

Link to the scientific paper [here](#).

Link to the scientific paper through CHESSETUP website section [here](#).

- Scientific paper 3:

“Domestic demand-side response: the challenge for heat pumps in a future UK - decarbonized heating market” (Selected Papers from the World Renewable Energy Congress WREC 2018)

Published in: Renewable Energy and Sustainable Buildings, 735-745, Book Chapter, Springer Link, August 2019

Author/s: NJ Hewitt, N Shah, D Cotter, C Wilson, K Le, R Byrne, P MacArtain, Ming Jun Huang

Abstract: (...) Building insulation programs will reduce heating loads, but experiences have illustrated that current UK best practice lags somewhat behind our European counterparts. Energy demands for heat pumps would therefore reduce and efficiencies would increase depending on the depth of retrofit. The rates of retrofit may require 2050 targets to be met by active energy systems rather than the passive roles of insulation. Demand-side management in its many shapes and forms becomes part of the solution. The thermal mass of buildings can be deployed to understand duration of off-times after a period of heating while maintaining thermal comfort. Understanding end-user behavior is critically important in this process as it is believed that the smart learning of the behavior of the building can be subtly tailored to end-user needs. Selective fabric retrofits and selective occupancy controls can adjust these parameters, further giving an element of control to the end-user while satisfying electricity network operator needs (...).

Link to the scientific paper [here](#).

Link to the scientific paper through CHESSE SETUP website section [here](#).

- Scientific paper 4:

“Tariff-based load shifting for domestic cascade heat pump with enhanced system energy efficiency and reduced wind power curtailment”

Applied Energy
Volume 257, 1 January 2020, 113976

Published in: ELSEVIER - Applied Energy, Volume 257, 1 January 2020, 113976

Author/s: Khoa Xuan Le, Ming Jun Huang, Nihilkumar N. Shah, Christopher Wilson, Neil J. Hewitt

Abstract: Cascade air-to-water heat pumps may have good potential for retrofitting UK domestic buildings because they can directly replace existing fossil-fuel boilers without the requirement of considerable modifications to heat distribution systems. A widespread uptake of these heat pumps, however, would pose challenges to the grid. Furthermore, wind power generation has increased in the UK to achieve the target of decreasing CO₂ emissions by 2050, but there are high levels of wind curtailment due to the mismatch between electricity supply and demand. In this paper, a load shifting study for cascade heat pumps coupled with thermal energy storage addressing these issues is presented. The main objective is to find the best tariff-based schedule load shifting for cascade heat pumps, which can help to avoid peak demand periods while obtaining enhanced system energy efficiency with minimized running costs and reduced wind energy curtailment. How the retrofit performance of the cascade heat pumps with load shifting is further investigated. TRNSYS was used to simulate the system performance validated against experimental results. Northern Ireland (UK) was selected as the evaluated scenario. Simulation results showed that the tank temperature set point of 75 °C and the storage size of 1.2 could wholly shift the cascade heat pumps' operation to off-peak periods. The best times to start the cascade heat pumps to charge the storage were at 3 am and 2 pm for the morning and afternoon heating demands, respectively. Compared to oil boilers, the cascade heat pumps with load shifting could obtain lower running costs (16–34%) and carbon emissions (20–37%).

Link to the scientific paper [here](#).

Link to the scientific paper through CHESSE SETUP website section [here](#).

5. Conclusions: Impact of articles published

A set of general Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for evaluating the progress and impact of the communication and dissemination activities was presented in the plan of Deliverable 7.1.

TYPE OF CHANNEL	Echo	General
Social media/Newsletter	N° subscribers/followers Popularity of the messages Audience of the subscribers Initial meeting w/ stakeholders	Publications' frequency N° types of newsletters (adaptation to the public)
Website	N° direct contacts from form Questions asked N° documentation downloads N° views of the promotional video	Uploads' frequency FAQ's edition (Y/N) Infography edition Video (Y/N)
Clustering Activities	N° people attending presentation N° people stopping at the stand Initial meeting w/ stakeholders Relevant informations gathered N° people attending the kick off meeting N° people attending the final conference	N° abstracts sent N° attending event Time spent on strategic watch Time spent on workshops' organisation
Local events	N° people attending People's involvement	N° meetings organised Positive evaluation
One-to-one communication	N° people concerned N° of new contacts Relevant informations gathered	Average time spent answering Time spent canvassing potential stakeholders Follow-up of this exchanges
Press	N° edited N° publications in journals/magazines/portals N° publications in generalist journals/magazines/portals Audience of the publications	Abstracts, articles sent Contact with journalists/editors N° Press Releases

Figure 5. KPIs for type of channel for communicate and disseminate activities during CHESSE SETUP Project. (Source: D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan, CHESSE SETUP Project).

In the case of the **Divulgarion Articles** these KPIs are finally adapted as follows:

- **Type of channel:** for communicate and disseminate the project.

Press, portals or media agencies

- **General:** referring to the **input** indicators.

1. Number of article/s sent
2. Number of contact/s with journalists/editors

- **Echo:** referring to the **output** indicators which give the impact of the activity.

3. Number of article/s published
 - 3.1. Number of publication/s in more generalist journals/magazines/portals
 - 3.2. Number of publication/s in more specialized journals/magazines/portals

4. Number of type/s of audience or stakeholders/target groups reached via the final journals/magazines/portals (following the stakeholders and targets exposed in Figure 2).

In the case of the **Press Releases** these KPIs are finally adapted as follows:

- **Type of channel:** for communicate and disseminate the project.

Press, portals or media agencies

- **General:** referring to the **input** indicators.

1. Number of press release/s written

- **Echo:** referring to the **output** indicators which give the impact of the activity.

2. Number of press releases published
3. Number of types of audience or stakeholders/target groups reached via the final journals/magazines/portals (following the stakeholders and targets exposed in Figure 2).

In the case of the **Scientific Papers** these KPIs are finally adapted as follows:

- **Type of channel:** for communicate and disseminate the project.

Scientific Journals

- **General:** referring to the **input** indicators.

4. Number of scientific papers submitted

- **Echo:** referring to the **output** indicators which give the impact of the activity.

5. Number of scientific papers published
6. Impact factor of the journal where the paper is published
7. Impact factor of the paper (or number of downloads as an alternative, if it is not possible to retrieve the first)
8. Cite score of the paper

In conclusion, in the following infographic (Figure 6) the **final results or impact indicators of CHESS SETUP divulgation articles, press releases and scientific papers** are shown (Last retrieved: 28/09/2020):

DIVULGATION ARTICLES

Input 3 Divulcation articles sent 3 Contacts with journalists/editors

Echo 3 Divulcation article published (edited internally)

1 in a Generalist medium

2 in a Specialized medium

6 Extra Divulcation article published (edited externally)

CHESSETUP

Jun 2016
Sep 2020

PRESS RELEASES

4 Press releases internally written

At least

4 Press releases published

1. "Birth of CHESSETUP" Aug 2016
2. "CHESSETUP in practice" Apr 2018
2. "CHESSETUP is advancing" Sep 2019
4. "CHESSETUP ..." Jul 2020

8 Press releases published (edited externally)

SCIENTIFIC PAPERS

4 Scientific papers submitted to scientific journals or books

4 Scientific papers published in scientific journals or books

1. "High temperature air source heat pump coupled with thermal energy storage: comparative performances and retrofit analysis" Feb 2019

SJR ² of Energy Procedia – Elsevier Journal: 0.545 (2019)

Paper's Reader/s : 31 Paper's Citation/s : 1

2. "Techno-economic assessment of cascade air-to-water heat pump retrofitted into residential buildings using experimentally validated simulations" Sep 2019

SJR ² of Applied Energy – Elsevier Journal: 3.455 (2019)

Paper's Reader/s : 41 Paper's Citation/s : 3

3. "Domestic demand-side response: the challenge for heat pumps in a future UK - decarbonized heating market" Aug 2019

Renewable Energy and Sustainable Buildings - Springer Book Downloads (alternative): 43k
Paper's Downloads (alternative): 740

4. "Tariff-based load shifting for domestic cascade heat pump with enhanced system energy efficiency and reduced wind power curtailment" Jan 2020

SJR ² of Applied Energy – Elsevier Journal: 3.455 (2019)

Paper's Reader/s : 24 Paper's Citation/s : 4

6 stakeholders/target groups* reached combining the 3 channels

*More information in D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan

² Scientific Journal Rank: measure of journal's impact, influence and prestige. It expresses the average number of weighted citation received by the documents published in the journal in the 3 years previous years.

Figure 6. CHESSETUP Articles Infographic with results and impact. (Source: Own elaboration)

Deliverable 7.7